

Improvement of Equal Cooperation by Adolescent Characteristics and Time-Series Learning and Predicting Abilities of Recurrent Q-Learning Agents in Interrole-Conflict Game

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Abstract: People can typically be classified as belonging to multiple groups, and in such situations "interrole conflicts" may occur. Studies on interrole conflicts have mainly targeted adult subjects, although they can occur before the developmental stage of adulthood. In addition, few studies have been conducted on interrole conflicts experienced during adolescence. Furthermore, simulation studies of interrole conflicts are scarce, with the exception of our previous study. This study aimed to clarify the differences in coping abilities in interrole-conflict situations between adolescence and adulthood. In our previous study, we proposed an interrole-conflict game (ICG) as a new game-theoretic framework to deal with interrole conflicts. This study adopts recurrent Q-learning (RQL) agents with adolescent or adult characteristics and time-series learning and predicting abilities as new players of the ICG. Our simulation experiment results found that not only the high learning rate and the low discount rate caused typical adolescent characteristics, but also the time series learning and predicting abilities which controlled by the prefrontal cortex played important roles to cope with interrole conflict and to emerge and improve an equal cooperation among people in the interrole conflict situation. Furthermore, it is suggested that middle childhood or pubertal individuals can cooperate equally if it is possible to increase the amount of serotonin in the subjects.

Keywords: Adolescent characteristics, improvement of equal cooperation, interrole-conflict game, recurrent Q-learning, time-series learning and predicting abilities.

I. INTRODUCTION

People can typically be classified as belonging to multiple groups, and in such situations "interrole conflicts" may occur. As shown in Fig. 1, interrole conflict occurs when people belonging to multiple groups are simultaneously requested to work by these groups [1-2]. In addition, interrole conflicts occur frequently in places where people belonging to multiple groups gather, regardless of their generation or role. In other words, interrole

Fig. 1 Interrole-conflict situation in which a person requests work simultaneously and belongs to many groups.

conflicts occur not only after the developmental stage of adulthood but also in adolescent groups. However, most studies of interrole conflict have focused on adult subjects.

Adolescence—the period between childhood and adulthood—is a time in which ego identity is formed and the mental and physical foundations of life after adolescence are built [3]. In contrast, in early adulthood, the prefrontal cortex matures, which suppresses impulsive behavior and plays an important role in executing plans in the proper order [4]. The inability of adolescents to perform actions in an orderly and systematic manner is thought to be due to the immaturity of their prefrontal cortex. It was also found that differences in the degree of development of these brain regions cause peculiar behavioral characteristics from an adolescent perspective [5]. As mentioned above, adolescents exhibit characteristics that are different from those of adults. Therefore, focusing only on adulthood to elucidate the emergence and transformation processes of coping strategies is

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insufficient to alleviate the interrole conflicts that cause various problems. In other words, we must prepare multiple populations organized by dividing human subjects according to their adolescent and adult characteristics and observe interactions among the groups for a prolonged period.

When such experiments with human subjects are difficult, a Multi-Agent Simulation (MAS) experiment can demonstrate its true potential. However, there are almost no studies concerning interrole conflicts targeting both adolescents and adults using MAS, except for our previous study [6]. In our previous study, we investigated how behaviors in interrole-conflict situations differ between adolescents and adults using MAS consisting of Q-learning-only agents. The MAS results suggested that high learning rate and low discount rate that caused typical adolescent characteristics, which included risk-taking, impulsivity and novelty seeking, played important roles in coping with interrole conflict and promoting equal cooperation among people in interrole-conflict situations.

Another way to solve interrole conflict is random action selection or guesswork; however, our previous work showed that the performance of Q-learning only agents is superior to that of agents who act completely randomly. In interrole-conflict situations, it is necessary to properly predict what actions the members of each group will choose, and in what order. In other words, each member must make excellent use of the time-series learning and predicting abilities. Our previous study adopted simple Q-learning-only agents, without these abilities. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of time-series learning and prediction abilities on solving interrole-conflict situations and how behaviors based on these abilities differ between adolescents and adults. Therefore, we adopted recurrent Q-learning (RQL) agents [7] with these abilities. Elucidating these questions may lead to solutions to interrole conflicts that arise even after adulthood. This is also extremely important in pursuing good physical, mental, and social conditions, namely well-being.

II. INTERROLE CONFLICT GAME

A. An interrole conflict expressed by game-theoretic framework

As shown in Fig. 1, an interrole conflict occurs when people belonging to multiple groups are requested to simultaneously perform work by

those groups. To express this interrole-conflict situation as a game-theoretic framework, the following three conditions must be met: 1) people can belong to multiple groups; 2) they can cooperate with only one group at a time; and 3) they can benefit from the cooperation of others, except for themselves. However, no game meets all the three conditions. Therefore, in our previous study [6], we proposed an interrole-conflict game (ICG) with the above three characteristics as a novel game that expresses interrole-conflict situations.

Fig. 2 shows a schematic diagram of the minimum configuration of ICG when the number of players and groups are three, respectively and the maximum number of groups to which each person can belong is two. In this study, we adopt the ICG with this minimum configuration, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Schematic of an interrole-conflict game (ICG) minimum configuration, in which there are three players and groups, and the maximum number of groups to which each person belongs is two.

Players of the ICG can receive three types of rewards: 1) R^+ when $S > 1$, 2) 0 when $S = 1$, and 3) R^- when $S < 1$, where S is the bare minimum number of cooperative people in a group, R^+ is a positive reward, and R^- is a negative reward. The sum of rewards reaped from all groups to which the player belongs is given to that player. For example, as shown in Fig. 2, the player-A who belongs to both group 1 and 2 receives " $R^+ + R^-$," whereas player-B who belongs to both group 2 and 3 receives " $0 + R^-$," and player-C who belongs to both group 1 and 3 receives " $R^+ + 0$."

Based on the reward function, the optimal solution in ICG with the minimum configuration is to rotate three groups in turn, such that the two players cooperate in each group.

B. Recurrent Q-learning agents with characteristics of adolescence and adulthood as players of the ICG

We adopt RQL agents [7] as the ICG players. RQL [7] is a hybrid learning method between Q-

learning [8-9]—known as one of the reinforcement learning methods—and recurrent neural network (RNN) as a learning framework with time-series learning and predicting capabilities [10]. We use a modified model [11] of the Elman-net [12] as one of the architectures of RNNs. The ϵ -greedy policy [8-9] is adopted as the method for selecting actions. A schematic view of the learning process flow in RQL is shown in Fig.3.

Fig. 3 Schematic of the learning process flow in recurrent Q-learning. The numbers circled from 1 to 7 represent the processing order.

As can be seen in Fig.3, first, the RNNs of RQL agents receive the actions of the opponents at time $t-1$, output their Q-values, which represent the worth of the agents' actions, and select one of the actions based on the Q-values by using the ϵ -greedy policy. Thereafter, the rewards are received, and their Q-values are renewed using Q-learning. Finally, in the RQL, the renewed Q-values become the teacher signals for the RNN, and the RNN learns to output the renewed Q-values using the back-propagation method with a learning rate η .

In the ICG, each player selects one group to which they belong that cooperates by themselves during every step. Therefore, the types of player actions are identical to the number of groups to which they belong. The states that are necessary to select an action are the group numbers selected by all players at time $t-1$.

Differences in characteristics of adolescence and adulthood can be represented by settings of three parameters in the RQL agents: the learning rate η of the RNN and the learning and discount rates of the Q-learning, namely, α and γ , respectively. Two types of learning rates can be interpreted as follows; α is the amount of change that determines how fast we can approach the target Q-value, and η is the amount of change that determines how large to change the weight of each connection line of the RNN that outputs the updated Q-value.

We interpret that the plasticity of the brain is expressed by two types of learning rates, and the discount rate for Q-learning corresponds to serotonin, a neurotransmitter in the brain. Therefore, adolescents with high plasticity and low serotonin concentrations can be represented by an RQL agent with a high learning rate and low discount rate. In contrast, adults with low plasticity and high serotonin concentrations can be represented by those with low learning rates and high discount rates.

III. RESULTS

A. Settings of the simulation experiments

The parameters used in ICG simulation experiments are listed in Table 1*.

Table 1 Settings of simulation experiments.

Maximum number of steps	1,000,000
The number of players (agents)	3
The number of groups	3
The number of groups to which one player can belong	2
The bare minimum number of cooperation in a group S	1
Rewards R^+ and R^-	+1 and -1
The number of output neurons in RNN	2
The number of input neurons in RNN	3
The number of hidden (context) neurons in RNN	3 patterns = {1, 5, 10}
The degree of randomness ϵ in action selection for the ϵ -greedy policy	0.1
Learning rate α for Q-learning	9 patterns = {0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9}
Discount rate γ for Q-learning	9 patterns = {0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9}
Learning rate η used by the BP for RNN	3 patterns = {0.1, 0.5, 0.9}

The MAS experiments of the ICG use each setting independently, as shown in Tables 1, and are conducted for every forty different random seeds.

* In our previous study [6], 0.01 and 0.99 were included as the learning and discount rates for the Q-learning. In this study, we omit these values, because RQL agents cannot completely learn when their values are set.

B. Results of the simulation experiments

First, we confirm the average number of cooperation in each group when two players are gathered into one group. To compare with an MAS experiment that consists of three RQL agents, we determine a baseline for such numbers by using complete random players with no learning. As shown in Fig.4, the baseline of the average number of cooperation was approximately 250,000.

As can be understood from the rule used to obtain points in the ICG, the optimum and maximum number of cooperation is approximately 333,333 points. That is, by realizing three periodic rotations among the three agents when the game is up to 1,000,000 steps.

Fig. 4 Average number of cooperation in each group in the case of two players gathered in one group and earned using the MAS experiment, which consisted of three completely random players. The baseline cooperation number is approximately 250,000.

Next, by illustrating the heatmaps of the average number of cooperation in each group confirmed by the MAS experiments with all parameters, we summarized the differences in the influences of all parameters, such as the two types of learning rates η and α , and the discount rate γ on the emergence of cooperation.

To compare the results of the Q-learning-only agents with those of the RQL agents, we first show the former in Fig.5. Here, we find that the Q-learning-only agents as the ICG players, realize more cooperation than the baseline made

by the complete random players. In most cases where γ is lower than 0.2, the number of cooperation becomes larger than 280,000 whenever α is set to any value. The number of cooperation peaks when α is set to 0.6 and γ is 0.1. The average number of cooperation at this peak was 290,464, which is a difference of approximately 40,000 compared to the completely random player results.

$\alpha \setminus \gamma$	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9
0.1	279266	279749	276234	273022	270868	269752	268372	266356	265359
0.2	282447	281153	278731	275503	272771	271126	269268	267250	265899
0.3	284413	281889	279017	276204	273572	271276	269148	267700	266499
0.4	286291	282480	279080	276459	273714	271326	269309	267557	266350
0.5	288467	283343	279235	276292	273488	270789	268784	266983	265984
0.6	290464	283897	279207	275321	272651	270016	267795	266289	265155
0.7	286789	281770	277276	274071	271071	268193	266133	264733	264207
0.8	281674	276854	273354	270862	268353	265931	263872	262803	262686
0.9	276185	270507	268392	266721	264831	262687	260929	260064	260562

Fig. 5 Average number of cooperation in the three groups in the case where two players are gathered in one group earned by the MAS experiments, which consists of three Q-learning-only players per parameter. The x- and y-axes represent the values of γ and α , respectively. The yellow value (290,464) indicates a peak.

Thereafter, we depict the heatmaps of the average number of cooperation earned by the MAS experiments that consist of three RQL players for different parameters in Fig.6. Fig.6 is different from Fig.5 in that it shows the results of checking the effects of the learning rate η used by the BP method and the number of hidden neurons of the RNN on the number of cooperation. The x- and y-axes of the table outer frame in Fig.6 shows the number of hidden neurons and the learning rate η for the RNN, respectively.

Fig. 6 Average numbers of cooperation in the three groups in case where two players are gathered in one group earned by the MAS experiments, which consists of three RQL players per parameters. The x- and y-axes of the outer frame of table show the number of hidden neurons and the learning rates η for the RNN, respectively. The x- and the y-axes of each heatmaps are the same of Fig. 5. It can be seen that the red cells in all heatmaps of Fig.6, where mean values of the number of cooperation is over 280,000, are higher than that of Fig.5. Moreover, the RQL agents, for which the learning rate η is 0.1, changed classes completely. As can be confirmed from the results when setting the above parameter, the number of cooperation in the RQL agents that changed classes was over 300,000. Furthermore, as the number of hidden neurons is increased, the times of cooperation are also increased in case that the learning rate η is 0.1 and 0.5.

It can be seen that the red cells in all heatmaps of Fig.6, where mean values of the number of cooperation is over 280,000, are more than that of Fig.5. By reviewing Fig.6, we find that the smaller the learning rate η , the greater the number of cooperation. When taking note of the learning rate α and the discount rate γ

of the Q-learning part in the RQL agents, we find that the ratio of the learning rate α to be the peak of the number of cooperation is 0.5 to 0.9, which is higher than the cooperation of the Q-learning only agents. The number of cooperation peaks when the discount rate γ for Q-learning is 0.7 to 0.9, except for cases in which

the learning rate η for the RNN is 0.1 and 0.5 when the number of hidden neurons is 1.

In all cases, the peak values of the number of cooperation are over 296,000, which is higher than the value of the Q-learning-only agents. Moreover, the RQL agents, for which the learning rate η is 0.1, changed classes completely. As can be confirmed from the results when setting the above parameter, the number of cooperation in the RQL agents that changed classes was over 300,000. Furthermore, as the number of hidden neurons is increased, the times of cooperation are also increased in case that the learning rate η is 0.1 and 0.5.

As the learning rate η for the RNN is increased, the red colors of each cell are diluted; that is, the number of cooperation decreased. Furthermore, when the learning rate η is 0.9, the number of hidden neurons is 5 and 10, and the learning rate α is greater than 0.7, the number of cooperation decreases.

Finally, as a summary, we compared the results of the peak-only number of cooperation per parameter in the RNN to clarify the effect of the learning rate η and the number of hidden neurons in the RNN on the results.

Fig. 7 illustrates the changes in the peak number of cooperation for the three types of learning rates η for the RNN when the numbers of hidden neurons are 1, 5, and 10. As shown in Fig. 7, as the learning rate η increases, the peak number of cooperation decreases, regardless of the number of hidden neurons except for that of the neurons is 5.

Fig. 7 Peak number of cooperation for three types of learning rates η for the RNN when the numbers of hidden neurons are 1, 5, and 10. As shown in Fig. 7, as the learning rate η increases, the peak number of cooperation decreases, regardless of the number of hidden neurons except for that of the neurons is 5.

Let us change the way we examine the peak number of cooperation. Fig. 8 shows the peak number of cooperation for each of the three types of hidden neurons in the RNN when the learning rates η are 0.1, 0.5, and 0.9. The smaller the learning rate η , the greater the number of cooperation, except for the learning rate η is 0.9. As can be seen in Fig. 8, the peak number of cooperation when the learning rate η is 0.1 is increased, as the number of hidden neurons is increased.

Fig.8 Peak number of cooperation of three types of hidden neurons in the RNN when learning rates η are 0.1, 0.5, and 0.9. The smaller the learning rate η , the greater the number of cooperation, except for the learning rate η is 0.9.

IV. DISCUSSION

In this section, we discuss the effects of each parameter of the RQL agents, including the characteristics of adolescence or adulthood on the number of cooperation.

Our adopted RQL agent model as a player of the ICG has three types of parameters concerning RNN and Q-learning: the learning rate η for the RNN and the learning and discount rates α and γ for Q-learning. By using these parameters, we can characterize RQL agents as adolescent or adult subjects.

Doya [13] proposed a hypothesis that serotonin controls the timescale of reward prediction and acetylcholine controls the speed of memory updates. The learning rate α is a parameter that determines the amount of action value update. If the learning rate α is large, the agent drastically changes the values of their actions according to the reward received. The learning rate α corresponds to acetylcholine. The discount rate γ was used to determine which immediate and delayed rewards were emphasized. As the brain learns, related

to the discount rate, Okamoto *et al.* [14] showed that serotonin plays an important role in controlling the timescale parameter for reward prediction. Based on the above results, the discount rate γ represents the amount of serotonin. Therefore, adolescent individuals with high brain plasticity and low concentrations of serotonin can be represented by an RQL agent with a high learning rate α and low discount rate γ . In contrast, adults with low brain plasticity and high concentrations of serotonin can be represented by an RQL agent with a low learning rate α and a high discount rate γ .

Then, how can the learning rate η of the RNN in the RQL agent be interpreted? The RQL agent adopted in this study has the RNN as a system for predicting the values of his/her actions. The RNN learns the combination of the states observed from the environment and the teacher signals using the BP method. In the RQL agent, the Q-values renewed using Q-learning become teacher signals. By learning using the BP method, the RQL agent can output the predicted values of his/her actions that are thought to be conducted, namely, the renewed Q-values. Therefore, in the RQL agent, brain plasticity can be represented by the learning rate η for the RNN, and the renewed Q-values can be interpreted as a temporary goal that expresses the orientation of such dynamic changes in the brain.

Compared to adult brains, adolescent brains have high plasticity that dynamically change the synapses, neurons, and axons [15-17]. Konrad *et al.* [18] suggest that there is a possibility that typical adolescent behavior patterns, which include risk-taking, are caused by the high plasticity of the adolescent brain. Based on these suggestions, we presume that agents with high learning rates can be regarded as adolescent individuals with high plasticity who can change their actions rapidly and can easily show cooperation in the ICG. The players who can rapidly change their action values according to immediate rewards when judging their actions are bad-win an advantage over players who cannot in the ICG, because it is difficult near future results in this game. In fact, when the learning rate η for the RNN is 0.1, as can be seen in Fig. 6, our simulation results showed that the RQL agents with a high learning rate α and low discount rate γ for Q-learning achieved a greater number of equal cooperation than those with a low learning rate α and a high discount rate γ , as is the case with the results of the Q-learning-only agents adopted in our previous study [6]. In an eminently volatile ICG, where there was no guarantee that other individuals

would continue to cooperate with the same group, this agent would be less dependent on expected rewards by having a low discount rate. As a result, relatively equal cooperation could be maintained.

Another interpretation is that when the RQL agents can obtain some time structure, such as a three periodic rotation for changing their actions during the early steps, and if the RQL agents have a high learning rate η , they are disadvantaged because such a high learning rate can destroy the time structure made in their RNN. However, it may be possible to offset the destruction of the time structure in the RNN because of its high learning rate η . This is because it is possible to learn actions that prioritize future expected rewards when the discount rate γ in Q-learning is high. In general, it is known that the subject in childhood has higher plasticity than the subject in adolescence, and the prefrontal cortex, which is responsible for time-series learning and prediction abilities, is more immature. Therefore, it is extremely difficult for children with such characteristics to form a state of equal cooperation in the ICG. In the case where the RQL agents have high learning rates η greater than 0.9, the results in Fig. 6 suggest that ICG, which seems difficult to solve for those subjects, can be resolved to some extent if the amount of serotonin in childhood subjects is increased.

Commonly, as the number of hidden neurons is increased, the RNN can acquire some complex function like a chaos system. However, the rule and function that are acquired by the RNN with many neurons can be easily destroyed in case that the learning rate η is very high, as illustrated in Fig. 6.

V. CONCLUSION

Few studies have investigated interrole conflicts among adolescents. Hence, this study aimed to clarify the differences in coping abilities between adolescence and adulthood in interrole-conflict situations. In our previous study [6], we proposed an ICG as a novel game-theoretic framework that represented the situation of interrole conflict and adopted the ICG used in this study. Furthermore, as players in the ICG, we adopted RQL agents with the characteristics of adolescents or adults.

Our simulation experiment results found that not only high learning rate and low discount rate that caused typical adolescent characteristics which included risk-taking, impulsivity, and novelty seeking, but also the time series learning and predicting abilities,

which controlled by the prefrontal cortex played important roles in coping with interrole conflict as well as in emerging and improving equal cooperation among people in interrole-conflict situations. Furthermore, it is suggested that middle childhood or pubertal individuals can cooperate equally if it is possible to increase the amount of serotonin in the subjects. Moreover, we clarified that the high discount rate γ is required to form the cooperation, as the number of hidden neurons is increased, like development from adolescent to adulthood.

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